

Bioaccumulation to be Polluted by Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) in the Serum of Patients Admitted to Al-Rifai General Hospital in Al-Rifai District

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Abstract

The study started from January Until December 2022 to measure the Concentration rate of Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in the blood serum of People who visited Al-Rifai General Hospital in Al-Rifai district, north of DhiQar Governorate, which is located near the Garraf oil field, north of Nassiriya city.

The present study included the collection of 40 samples with ages ranging from (19 to 60) years, it divided into three groups, and the study adopted 15 samples of People who do not have a specific disease as a control group and 13 samples were from people with diabetes and 12 from pregnant women.

The apparent results and statistical analysis showed that the concentration of PAHs in Diabetics and Pregnant women was higher than the concentration in healthy people (control). The present study showed that the concentration of PAHs for Diabetics and Pregnant was with a mean (95.7 ± 11.6636), (92.23 ± 9.782323) ng/ml, while the concentration of PAHs for healthy people was with a mean (92.23 ± 9.782323) ng/ml.

Keywords: *Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), Al-Gharaf river, pregnant women, diabetes.*

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Introduction

Air

Atmospheric pollution is the finding of chemicals in the atmosphere, particulates, or biological materials that cause discomfort, disease, or death to humans, damage other living organisms and food crops, or damage the environment surrounding living organisms (Sharma *et al.*, 2013). In line with (Choudhary and Garg, 2015), the substances present in the air that can be harmful to humans and the environment are known as air pollutants. They can be in the form of liquid droplets, solid particles, or gases. In addition, they may be natural or man-made.

Pollution has increased, especially with the increase in the extraction and consumption of crude oil, especially in recent years. There is also a relationship between the economy and pollution. (Al-Yasiri and M. T. Khathi 2016), (Al Rukabie and J. H. Kadhum 2020). The term environment refers to the atmosphere surrounding the earth, water, soil, and living organisms that live on the earth. The biosphere is vast and complex, but it is divided into parts based on the interaction between living organisms and

the environment in which they live, such as the earth, water, and air. Anything that works to damage or disrupt the physical or biological systems in this environment, directly or indirectly, is classified as pollution. (Feng *et al.*, 2024).

The issue of pollution has become a more widespread factor due to the rising levels of greenhouse gases in the air or atmosphere, the emissions of gases that cause this problem worldwide, and the factors that accompany it such as climate change and environmental depletion. (G. Aziz *et al.*, 2023). Pollution is any gradual or sudden change in the chemical, physical, or biological properties of the environment. When these pollutants increase, governments may resort to imposing fines on polluters to preserve the environment and achieve environmental goals. (K. Dong *et al.*, 2022). Air pollution is the release of pollutants into the atmosphere that are effect harmful to the environment around humans and organisms (UNEP,2003).

Industrial

The industry is the main source of environmental pollution and has a negative impact on living organisms, especially human health, where the industry takes the water they need in the process of industrialization from rivers, lakes and after that, It is returned to their industrial water to rivers after loaded with Industrial pollutants (organic and non-organic) and toxic pollutants. Their accumulation in rivers leads to Being transmitted to humans through the consumption of drinking water or to fish and other living organisms through the food chain, including humans, and causes intestinal diseases of humans such as E. coli, salmonella typhi and Vibrio cholera etc.

Baghdad has many industries that use water during the production process and then push water to the river directly or after a limited treatment, or discharge it to the networks of the city's sewage after polluting with a lot of organic and inorganic matter suspended or dissolved or floating.

Food

The daily food industry targets more than 645 m³ / h containing organic pollutants and water discharges from the dairy industry which contain fatty substances, cheese, and milk residues. These manufactory do not contain treatment units. (Saeed,2000).

PAHs

Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) It is considered a widely spread pollutant everywhere, with the ability to cause endocrine disorders, which have health effects on humans and public health. (Yin *et al.*,2017)

PAHs It is considered an environmental pollutant and can be released into the environment through many natural sources such as large forest fires and volcanic smoke. In recent years, human emissions have been responsible for the expansion of the release of these pollutants into the environment (Montano Soto and Garza Ocanas, 2014). PAHs are aromatic hydrocarbons with 2 or more benzene rings and do not contain hetero atom or carry substituents (Lawal, 2017). Detect about 500 different types from it in the environment, but benzo(a)pyrene has been given greater attention among the whole PAHs family, Because of its carcinogenic activity. (Kisku et al., 2018). Humans are exposed to PAHs through skin contact, ingestion, or Exposure to Large quantities of contaminant mixtures containing PAHs May cause eyes Irritation to the eyes, vomiting, nausea, diarrhea, skin irritation, and inflammations (Lawal, 2017). Studies have proven that PAHs have Influences carcinogenic, mutagenic and teratogenic effects on animals and humans (Singh *et al.*, 2008 ; Kisku et al., 2018).

Petrogenic PAHs Its natural source from oil seepages and erosion of petroliferous shales, and Natural resources of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons from combustion or pyrolysis include PAHs from incomplete burning wood materials and the big fires of forests and grasses. PAHs resulting from human activity inputs can result in similar, but It has nothing to do with PAH compounds and the collection of

PAHs to those of natural origin. PAH resulting from human activities is created from the subtraction into the environment of petrogenic PAHs through accidents that lead to large oil spills.

The researcher's data YANG *et al.*, 2017 indicated that suggested that elevated 4-hydroxyphenanthrene (4-OH Ph) found it was dose-responsive related to the Possible occurrence of diabetes in Workers who work in the coke oven. The number of years of work and total body mass should be taken into account when evaluating the risk of diabetes associated with occupational exposure to PAHs.

To measure exposure to polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in newborns and to determine their potential effect on reproductive hormones, they were verified and hormone levels were measured in the umbilical cords of 98 newborns and 98 mothers in Shengxi Islands. The average concentration of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons was found to be 164 ng g⁻¹ lipid, and 68 % of the polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons were lower molecule congeners. It was the highest level for pyrene (PYR) and naphthalene (NAP), and its percentage was 54.6 % of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons present in the biological samples. Exposure to pollution by polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons had a negative effect on both hormones estradiol (E2) and anti-mullerian (AMH) While it had a positive impact on FISH In fetal umbilical cord serum. In the endocrine system, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons can be considered as a type of chemical that disrupts its endocrine-disrupting chemical (EDC) (Yin *et al.*, 2017).

Materials and Methods

Sample Collection

The current study included the collection of 40 samples (aged from 19 years to 60 years) from People who visited Al-Rifai General Hospital in In Al-Rifai district, north of DhiQar Governorate Which is located near the Garraf oil field., north of Nassiriya City the withdrawal area was disinfected with a mild disinfectant, then blood was drawn from the radial vein, 10 ml of blood was obtained:

1. Blood was placed in the EDTA tube
2. All tubes are transferred in a cold box until the serum is separated to estimate PAHs.

Serum Preparation

We take 10 ml of the venous abscess and put it in the Centrifuge device (3000 rpm/min) Leave it in the device for 20 minutes, after that kept the serum at -20 ° C until serum was digested to estimate the concentration of PAHs.

Digestion of Serum

The method used (Ji and Ren, 2002) to digest serum which included an addition of two ml of nitric acid (70 %) and one ml of Perochloric acid (70 %) to (0.5)ml of serum in a Pyrex tube then heating of this compound with a water bath on a hot plate at (160 °C) for 1 hour, Then the mixture is cooled and completed to 10 ml with (30%) hydrochloric acid. Some modifications were done as the soaking of the serum in Nitric acid for thirty minutes, followed by the addition of Perchloric acid , and the increment of heating degree and period to 200°C and 2.5 hours respectively in order to obtain an absolute digestion of serum and vaporization of acids.

Measurement of PAHs

Half ml of the sample (serum) is placed in a conical flask and 100 ml of organic solvent (ethanol) is added. The sample is transferred to a vortex device and starts shaking for 15 minutes. Then let the solution settle down and place the extract in a test tube. The amount of the extract is taken and placed in the cell of the device (Sitelab-Ultraviolet fluorescence-3100) for examination. The amount of the extract is 3/4 of the

cell size, the cell is well wiped and placed in the device. Press the red test button where the device starts reading the desired sample concentration.

Study Area

To determine the probability of contamination of the area by Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), as well as the problem of pollution spread result of combustion operations and human activity, because of the presence of Al-Gharaf oil field, which was officially inaugurated in 2013 at Thi-Qar province Figure Rifai district south of the Gharaf Oil Field Figures 1 and 2 , Which is far away 12.8km from the south of the Garraf oil field.

Figure 1. The Place of Dhi Qar Governorate in the Map of Iraq

Figure 2. Location of Al -Gharaf Oil Field Site from Al-Rifai District

Results and Discussion

PAHs in Blood Serum of Study Persons

The mean concentrations of PAHs are determined for all samples in Table (1). The result shows the mean total concentration of PAHs for Healthy people exposed to pollution (Control) with a mean (72.5 ± 7.822146) ng /mL. While, the concentration rate of PAHs for Diabetics and Pregnant with a mean (95.7 ± 11.6636) (92.23 ± 9.782323) ng/mL.

Table 1. Concentrations (ng/mL) of PAHs in Blood Serum of Study Samples

	Group	N0	Mean PAHs \pm SD	P. Value Between the control and another group
PAHs	Healthy people exposed to pollution (Control)	15	72.5 ± 7.822146	
	Diabetics	14	95.7 ± 11.6636	0.001
	Pregnant	12	92.23 ± 9.782323	0.001

Table 2. Correlation Matrix in Control, Diabetics, and Pregnant in Study Stations

Samples	control	Diabetics	Pregnant
control	1		
Diabetics	0.823256	1	
Pregnant	0.821316	0.853724	1

Note: Correlation is significant at the 0.05

Figure 3. Accumulation PAHs in the Blood Serum ng/mL Comparison between Control, Diabetics, and Pregnant

The mean Concentrations of PAHs in blood serum for all age groups of Healthy people exposed to pollution (Control) are in Table (2). The result shows the highest frequent level of PAHs concentration in the third age group with a mean (75.13 ± 1.506911) ng/mL while, the lowest frequent level of PAHs concentration in the first age group with a mean (60.32 ± 7.089843) ng/mL.

Table 3. Concentrations (ng/mL) of PAHs in Serum Samples for Healthy People Exposed to Pollution (Control) Depending on the Age Group

	Group age	N0	Mean PAHs \pm SD
Healthy people exposed to pollution (Control)	19-30	5	60.32 ± 7.089843
	31-41	5	72.5 ± 2.957959
	42-53	5	75.13 ± 1.506911

Figure 4. Accumulation of PAHs in the Blood Serum ng/mL for (Control)

The mean Concentrations of PAHs in blood serum samples for all age groups of Diabetics are in Table (3). The result shows the highest frequent level of PAHs concentration in the third age group with a mean (85.24 ± 4.853765) ng/mL while, the lowest frequent level of PAHs concentration in the first age group with a mean (109.4 ± 8.671822) ng/mL.

Table 4. Concentrations (ng/mL) of PAHs in Serum Samples for Diabetics Depending on the Age Group

	Group age	N0	Mean PAHs±SD
Diabetics	30-40	4	85.24 ± 4.853765
	41-50	4	93.96 ± 2.845206
	51-60	5	109.4 ± 8.671822

Figure 4. Accumulation of PAHs in the Blood Serum ng/mL for Diabetics

The mean Concentrations of PAHs in blood serum samples for age groups of Pregnant in Table (3). The result shows the highest frequent level of PAHs concentration in the third age group with a mean (84.21 ± 5.431161) ng/mL while, the lowest frequent level of PAHs concentration in the first age group with a mean (101.5 ± 4.914023) ng/mL.

Table 5. Concentrations (ng/mL) of PAHs in Serum Samples for Pregnant Depending on the Age Group

	Group age	N0	Mean PAHs ± SD
Pregnant	18-25	6	84.21 ± 5.431161
	26-32	6	101.5 ± 4.914023

Figure 5. Accumulation of PAHs in the Blood Serum ng/mL for Diabetics

Discussion

PAHs concentration rate in blood serum. The adverse health effects of exposure to PAHs have become a major threat to public health, especially the people who live near the oil fields. Al-Rifai district is exposed to pollutants resulting from the burning of gas associated with oil extraction from the Al-Gharraf oil field to a great variety of contaminants, in particular to PAHs. This study was objective to measure the concentration rate of PAHs in serum samples.

This study shows that the PAHs levels in samples studied of humans exposed to pollution its high. This is because the Al Gharraf oil field is located north of the Al-Rifai district, and the burning of gas associated with oil extraction is directed by the winds towards the district, which exposes the city to the risk of pollution by PAHs. There was also a difference in the concentration of PAHs between groups of study . This study also recorded different values of PAHs concentration compared to global studies. The current study results showed that the concentration of PAHs for Healthy people exposed to pollution (Control). Diabetics and Pregnant was with a mean (72.5 ± 7.822146) (95.7 ± 11.6636) and (92.23 ± 9.782323) ng/mL respectively, and the highest frequent level of PAHs concentration in the Diabetics , while the lowest frequent level of PAHs concentration in the Healthy people exposed to pollution (Control), the results also showed statistically significant differences at $(p \leq 0.05)$. These levels of exposure to which the residents of the Al-Rifai district were exposed are similar or greater than the concentrations to which workers working in a petroleum refinery in Albania were exposed In a study conducted by Cipa et al., (2017) evaluation of PAHs in the serum of worker , the mean concentration of analytes in workers serum samples ranged from 6.07 to 140 ng/ mL for PAHs. The current study showed Higher concentrations of PAHs than In a previous study on Chinese populations highly exposed to PAHs the results (Zhiwen *et al.*, 2010) .

Although there is a discrepancy in the concentrations of PAHs in the totals of the study samples, all samples indicate the accumulation of large amounts of Petroleum cyclocarbons in the serum of the blood compared to previous studies and for all study samples, namely control, diabetics and pregnant women, and this may indicate the large volume of pollutants that are released in the study environment, where all samples recorded high levels of they live in the same area exposed to pollution, but the percentage of cyclic hydrocarbons was higher in diabetics and pregnant women and the high accumulation of PAHs in pregnant women may be due to the activity of the body for the pregnant mother and the amount of substances that she consumes during pregnancy or inhaled from the surrounding environment, which helps to enter large amounts of oil pollutants into the body to be less for patients with diabetes, and this may explain that its increase in pregnant women.

Research data by conducted by (YANG *et al.*, 2017) demonstrated a dose dependent relationship of urinary 4-OH Ph metabolites with the risk of diabetes in coke oven workers. Our results are in line with previous studies evaluating the contributions of environmental PAHs exposures on diabetes in the general population (Al-shaarawy *et al.*, 2016). In study conducted by (Alshaarawy *et al.*, 2016) found reported that individuals with increasing levels of urinary 1-OH Na, 2-OH Na, 2-OH Ph and group LMW PAHs were at a greater risk of diabetes

We also note in our current study a high percentage of the rate of PAHs in diabetics compared to control and pregnant women, where the tables and charts indicate that the largest percentage of the rate of hydrocarbons was in people with diabetes, perhaps this is due to dysfunction in the functions of organs, including the liver for diabetics, which reduces the body's resistance to the accumulation of these pollutants inside the body and the inability to process.

It has been observed that there is a relationship between the high concentration of PAHs and age, as the Human Age has increased, the rate of concentration of cyclic hydrocarbons in the blood serum has increased with the presence of the source of pollution, as shown in the current study and for all study

samples, as older people are more susceptible to pollution than younger people, perhaps due to the time period those in the Rifai area are exposed to permanent pollution from the nearby oil field, as well as foodstuffs located in the same The area as well as the inhalation of polluted air as a result of combustion processes in addition to other pollutants such as car exhausts and irregular burning operations in the same jurisdiction and as a result of increased activity due to the irregular population increase and the spread of laboratories and industrial activities accompanying the oil field.

There seems a relationship between the years of exposure, the nature of combustion products and the health effects of these pollutants in the human body. It was mentioned (Erhabor *et al.*, 2013) that PAHs exposure, that too high for 40 years of exposure and result in a relative risk of 1.2 – 1.4 for 2.2 for bladder cancer and lung cancer. In this study, we observed that the level of PAHs increases As a person gets older and a number of years of exposure. So it should monitor the level of pollution by PAHs in the serum of persons exposed to contamination of petroleum products to ensure that levels are kept at a minimum and nonharmful levels.

Conclusion

We conclude from the above research that patients with diabetes and pregnant women are more exposed to the accumulation of pollutants inside the body such as hydrocarbons and others if they are exposed to these pollutants from a direct or indirect source and their bodies are less able to process and remove it from the body due to dysfunction of organ functions, which may worsen the patient's health condition at a long-term level compared to healthy people (control), so we advise the above target groups, especially patients, to stay away from pollution places as much as possible and live in an environment less prone to pollution to prevent aggravation of pathological conditions, especially sick employees who work in companies that produce such pollutants.

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